

Colorimetric Estimation of 4-Cholesten-3-one using Zimmermann Reaction

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Manuscript received 18 March 1994, revised 28 December 1994, accepted 16 February 1995

Cholestenone (4-cholesten-3-one) an intermediate in the degradation of cholesterol. Cholesterol to cholestenone conversion is often used to study 3-hydroxysteroid oxidase activity¹. Glc and hplc are required to estimate cholestenone and cholesterol separately in a binary mixture². Selective estimation of cholestenone by its uv absorption following solvent extraction, involves hydrolysis of cholesterol esters by saponification and long incubation period³.

Zimmermann reaction is a well established reaction for the estimation of androsterones and 3- and 17-ketosteroids⁴. Cholestenone which is a 3-keto compound, gives Zimmermann reaction and can be selectively estimated in presence of cholesterol. Further, the method has also been used for the estimation of cholestenone produced during bioconversion of cholesterol by immobilised *Mycobacterium fortuitum* NRRL B-8153.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of Zimmermann chromogen of cholestenone revealed $\lambda_{\max}$ at 572.5. Using the calibration curve, the results of estimation of cholestenone in standard aliquots of known concentration is presented in Table 1. The calculated values of cholestenone are within the limits of experimental error.

The results of estimation of cholestenone during 3-hydroxysteroid oxidase using immobilised *M. fortuitum* NRRL B-8153 showed a clear increase in the amount of cholestenone with respect to time (Table 2). The maximum yield of cholestenone was observed at 72 h. The decrease in cholestenone content on prolonged incubation is due to its further breakdown by the action of 9-hydroxylase, an enzyme responsible for the steroid ring degradation, present in considerable level in *M. fortuitum* NRRL B-8153⁵.

The crystallised compound from the incubation medium (m.p. 80–81°) showed $\lambda_{\max}$ in ethanol at 241 nm. The ir spectra showed absence of OH and presence of C=O (1 700 cm^{-1}) as against the presence of OH (3 000–3 280

TABLE 2—AMOUNT OF CHOLESTENONE FORMED DURING 3-HYDROXYSTEROID OXIDASE ACTIVITY BY IMMOBILISED *M. fortuitum* NRRL B-8153

Incubation time h	Amount* $\pm$ SD $\mu\text{g/ml}$
24	0.023 $\pm$ 0.000
48	0.387 $\pm$ 0.001
72	0.450 $\pm$ 0.003
96	0.116 $\pm$ 0.004

*Mean of three replicates; $\pm$ SD = standard deviation.

cm^{-1}) and absence of C=O in the substrate. The nmr and mass spectral data confirmed the molecular weight of the compound as 384. The uv and ir spectra overlay on that of the authentic sample.

The present method requires no hydrolysis of cholesterol esters and no expensive instrumentation. The method, however, can not be used for the estimation of cholestenone in presence of other 3- or 17-ketosteroids like 4-androsten-3,17-dione, 1,4-androstadien-3,17-dione and progesterone as these steroids also respond to Zimmermann reaction.

Experimental

Authentic samples of cholesterol and 4-cholesten-3-one (Sigma) and pyridine and ethyl acetate (A.R.) were used as such. *M. fortuitum* NRRL B-8153 was obtained from Northern Regional Research Laboratory, Illinois.

Ethyl acetate solution of cholestenone containing 10 μg compound was vacuum-dried and Zimmermann reaction applied as follows. The residue was dissolved in 10% *m*-dinitrobenzene in pyridine (0.1 ml) and 2.5 M KOH (0.05 ml) was added. It was incubated at 45° for 30 min, then diluted with pyridine-ethyl acetate (1 : 1; 3 ml). The absorption was recorded in the range 400–800 nm on a Shimadzu 160 A spectrophotometer. Standard curve of cholestenone was prepared over the range of 10–60 μg .

Various concentrations from a stock solution of 4-cholesten-3-one in ethyl acetate, were pipetted and vacuum dried. Quantitative estimation of the residue was carried out using Zimmermann reaction as described above.

Immobilisation of microbial cells and biotransformation of cholesterol to cholestenone: *M. fortuitum* NRRL B-8153 was grown in the medium containing (g dm^{-3}) yeast extract (5.0), ammonium nitrate (1.0), K_2HPO_4 (0.25), $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.25), $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.001) and the pH adjusted to 7.0. The harvesting and entrapment of bacterial cells in polyacrylamide gel was done by the method de-

TABLE 1—AMOUNTS OF CHOLESTENONE IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION OF STANDARD ALIQUOT

Amount ($\mu\text{g}/0.1 \text{ ml}$)		%Error
Present	Estimated*	
10	10.39	+ 3.9
20	21.61	+ 8.0
30	31.71	+ 5.7
40	42.76	+ 6.9
50	52.25	+ 4.5

*Calculated using standard curve.

scribed earlier⁶. Experiments with entrapped bacterial cells were carried out in 30 ml tris-HCl buffer (0.01 M, pH 8.0; 50 ml) with 0.5 mg ml⁻¹ cholesterol concentration. Cholesterol was added using acetone as a carrier solvent.

Extraction and selective estimation of 4-cholesten-3-one : Samples (1 ml) of incubation medium were drawn after regular intervals and extracted with ethyl acetate (1 ml). The extract (0.1 ml) was used for colorimetric estimation using Zimmermann reaction as described above and 0.1 ml was used for tlc analysis (silica gel G). Plates were developed in benzene-ethyl acetate (5 : 1) and resolution detected by spraying the plates with 2% ceric ammonium sulphate in 60% H₂SO₄ and heating the plates at 110° for 15 min.

Complete disappearance of cholesterol and detection of a single bioconversion product permitted its direct crystallisation after extraction from the reaction medium using ethyl acetate. The extract, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, was evaporated to dryness, the residue crystallised from aqueous acetone and identified by co-tlc, m.p.,

uv, nmr, mass and overlay ir spectra.

Acknowledgement

The financial assistance from Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, New Delhi, is thankfully acknowledged.

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